

At transplanting, the surface soil in each drum was brought to the same puddled condition as that of the surrounding field. Water use in the open-bottom drum constituted evapotranspiration and deep percolation; water use in the closed-bottom drum constituted evapotranspiration alone.

Seedlings of rice variety Ratna were transplanted in mid-Jan. A 5-cm water level was maintained by refilling with a measured quantity of water. There was no rainfall during the growing season,

The highest water use through evapotranspiration (732.9 mm) and deep

percolation occurred from tillering to flowering (see table). Of a total 1999.5 mm water used by the crop, 56.4% met evapotranspiration needs; 43.5% was lost through deep percolation. □

Water balance in banded ricefields under different rainfed situations in Central India

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The Chhattisgarh region of Central India grows about 5 million ha of rice, 20% irrigated, the rest rainfed. Soil variability ranges from lateritic to clay to sandy loam and clay loam.

We examined the climatic water balance under banded field condition in three major riceland soils. We computed excessive, normal, and deficit rainfall situations for four stations using the Thornthwaite and Mather (1955) book-keeping procedure.

Rainfall and potential evapotranspiration values were used to obtain soil moisture storage, actual evapotranspiration, water deficit, and water surplus. We assumed that runoff occurred only with more than 10 cm standing water in banded ricefields, and percolation losses are always higher than runoff losses.

The two water losses were estimated under water surplus conditions in the water balance computations. The amount of water at field capacity was assumed to be 150 mm for sandy loam, 200 mm for clay loam, and 250 mm for clay soils, up to 1-m depth.

For annual rainfall data, three rainfall patterns were worked out for 1901-1987: excessive (greater than mean [MI + standard deviation [SD]], normal (M + SD to M - SD), and deficit (less than M - SD).

The probability of excessive rainfall pattern occurrence at the four stations ranged from 8 to 17%; that of normal

Water balance of different districts.

Parameter (mm)	Sandy loam (Matasi)			Clay loam (Dorsa)			Clay soils (Kanhar)		
	Excessive	Normal	Deficit	Excessive	Normal	Deficit	Excessive	Normal	Deficit
<i>Raipur</i>									
Rainfall	1813.5	1142.2	763.2	1813.5	1142.2	763.2	1813.2	1142.2	763.2
Percolation	1032.6	434.9	137.1	730.8	389.6	76.1	220.2	312.6	26.3
Runoff	85.1	0	0	262.9	0	0	398.3	27.2	0
<i>Rajnandgaon</i>									
Rainfall	2002.3	1232.2	682.4	2002.3	1232.2	682.4	2002.3	1232.2	682.4
Percolation	958.0	535.8	59.2	850.7	475.8	8.3	621.6	405.7	0
Runoff	75.2	0	0	323.1	10.0	0	724.1	29.7	0
<i>Durg</i>									
Rainfall	1736.5	1136.7	862.7	1736.7	1136.7	862.7	1736.9	1136.7	862.7
Percolation	981.2	450.5	244.8	390.5	390.5	193.8	580.5	314.8	137.6
Runoff	0	0	0	0	0	0	375.7	24.8	6.2
<i>Bilaspur</i>									
Rainfall	1475.6	1201.0	804.3	1475.6	1201.0	804.3	1475.6	1201.0	804.3
Percolation	970.9	462.1	153.2	499.4	390.1	103.2	399.4	348.3	52.7
Runoff	18.5	0	0	143.8	22.0	0	244.4	13.9	0

Annual rainfall (mm)

rainfall, from 61 to 77%; and that of deficit rainfall, from 10 to 22%.

The potential evapotranspiration required for water balance computation was worked out using Penman's (1948) equation. The normal value was considered for all three rainfall categories because the time series data required for calculation were unavailable. Moreover, all four stations were in the same agroclimatic region.

At all the stations and in all rainfall distribution categories, runoff losses were negligible compared with percolation losses in all soil types, except for clay soils under excessive rainfall (see table).

With deficit rainfall, even percolation losses were very low, with higher values in lighter soils. With normal rainfall, percolation losses accounted for 35-45% of light soil losses.

With decreasing rainfall (see figure)

and a major area under light soils, the cropping pattern must be diversified. But because most fields are banded and the region is a plains area, rice cultivation seems inevitable. Limited supplemental irrigation is important for rainfed rice in this area. Groundwater use through "dug" and "dug cum bore" wells may be suited to this region because of high percolation losses. □

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